

SPECIFIC ASPECTS OF TRAINING OF COACHES AND ATHLETES IN HANDBALL

¹Jammatov Jasurbek Sharipovich, ²Egamberganova Dilnoza Davronbekovna

¹Associate Professor (PhD) of the "Physical Culture Theory and Methodology" Department of Urganch State University

²Senior Lecturer of the "Sports Activities" department of Urganch State University

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Abstract. *The skills of the coach are seen in the effective management of the activities of the sports team, in the proper organization of training and education processes, considering the personal psychophysiological characteristics of each athlete. This article is dedicated to some characteristics of training coaches in handball.*

Keywords: *coach, training, handball, effective management.*

The growth of the system of training athletes in our country is due to the presence of personnel with a high level of professional qualification, the enthusiasm of talented athletes and coaches, and the scientific potential of specialists who are able to offer effective technologies and methods in the most promising directions for the further growth of sports results. In sports, learning occurs during training. The coach teaches his students, helps them improve their skills. Even talented and experienced athletes owe their success to their coaches. Some coaches work in mass sports, while others train future stars. In your coaching career, you may discover a talented athlete in the ordinary children's sports department. But for this, a special coaching talent is needed. Being a coach is a lot. Here are some things you should think about if you are a coach for a team [1].

If you start a job in a small or medium club, you should understand that this is a person who is deeply interested in sports, who is starting to become a versatile specialist. As much as possible, the trainer should be as follows.

Handball expert

To teach handball, you need to know handball. You must be able to show and explain to the players how to perform the exercises and be able to correct mistakes. You can't limit yourself to correcting and correcting mistakes, because the ability to see opportunities in handball is also very important.

Education specialist

The coach must be able to impart his knowledge and be familiar with the principles, methods and forms of training. For this he must know the following:

- state of training and skills of handball players;
- the effect of training on the body;
- dreams, hopes and goals of a handball player;
- understanding handball qualities, namely strength, endurance, agility, speed, as well as technique and tactics, etc.

Knowing all the rules of handball

The coach obviously knows the rules very well, but he has to teach the players the rules so they don't make mistakes.

He must know the rules very well so that he does not make mistakes and the referee does not decide against his team. If the ball is lost due to the coach's mistake, if the team is given 2 minutes, a fine and in the worst case - disqualification, this situation affects the team very badly.

Also, the coach must decide whether or not to appeal to the referee for decisions that are against the rules in youth and junior competitions.

Knows all the rules for keeping the time and scoreboard table and for actions in the substitution area

This set of rules explains how players should behave in the substitution area, and not understanding these rules can be costly, as mistakes can lead to a referee warning or, worse, a 2-minute suspension or suspension.

To be an expert on the rules of the competition

This set of rules provides information on which players can enter the team - promotion and relegation rules - completing their team's technical application - appealing the decision and more.

Therefore, the coach must familiarize himself with this regulation. If your local area has special rules for tournaments, that should also be noted.

doctor (physician)

Handball is a contact sport and sprains of fingers, ankles and feet are common. Therefore, it is very important that the coach can provide first aid to such injuries and not make them worse. The first correct action shown in injuries can shorten a player's recovery from an injury from months to days. At the same time, this move provides safety and security to handball players and parents knowing that help is close at hand in case of any injuries.

Organizer

The team has a match on Sunday - one player is sick and has to be replaced - one of the drivers said he can't take him to the match that day, so he has to find another transport - it became known that the opponents used sportswear of the same color as the sportswear of the coach's team in the game. The coach should always be ready for these situations before the trip to the opponent's field.

Organizer of bringing athletes to competitions

Often, the coach participates with his team in competitions that last a short or long day. It doesn't mean just getting on a bus or train and then: off we go! Questions to be asked: Are players allowed to compete? What is the best price? when do we leave What vehicle is used? (bus, train, private cars) When are we expected to return? Do we need more help? (Parents, other coaches). When you can find answers to these and other questions, you can go to the competition.

Leader

If the team consists of young people, it is necessary to hold a meeting with the coach, players and parents. It is necessary to prepare for this meeting, to prepare well in advance about the ideas and topics to be discussed.

Planner

Team training should be planned - both long-term and short-term - and daily training should be reflected in this planning.

Anticipate opponents

Knowing your opponent is an advantage when preparing for a match. What is their defense like (5-1, 6-0, 3-2-1) and what do we do about it? What will they use against us? What are we going to do about it?

Knowing your opponent allows you to develop tactics, but you also need to be prepared to change those tactics during the game if necessary.

Knowing the strengths and weaknesses of his team.

A coach should know the strengths and weaknesses of his players during the game and know how to use them in the best way during the game. This applies to their physical and mental aspects. A team consists of many players, each of them has its own characteristics, and knowing these individual characteristics well, the coach must be able to use them to improve the team's overall performance in the game.

To be a good representative for his club

Often, the coach introduces the club to the world by his behavior. A hysterical coach who yells and behaves negatively rarely leaves a good impression on the team, the opponent, the referees, and the audience.

To be a good representative for the game of handball

Handball games played well according to the rules are always a good advertisement for the sport. Good advertising keeps and encourages interest in playing handball.

To be a good representative for one's own person

By being a skilled and serious coach, he instills positive self-esteem. It is he who avoids arguments or disturbing things during the game or during the break and makes wise decisions. A skilled and respected coach does not have a situation where others (handball players, colleagues, parents, committee members) interfere in his work.

Diplomat

The team can be different. Conflicts can arise between players, between players and the coach, and the coach does not always have to be on one side, and the ability to resolve this conflict positively in this situation is very important for the coach, but whatever you do, resolve the conflict. You also need to understand that it is not.

A coach may be the only acceptable person for half of the team, while the other half finds training too difficult, too easy, too uninspiring, too complicated. Not everyone can be completely satisfied with the work of the coach, because everything is different in one way or another.

So, you have a preconceived idea of being a coach and you can take over your team and take responsibility of the team.

10 TIPS FOR A COACH

1. Be everywhere on time. Then you will have time to talk to people and learn about balls, sportswear, games and the like.

2. Always dress appropriately for the occasion (sports uniform or suit pants). It gives natural security and authority.

3. Be specific. Do not be careless and idle about the situation.

4. Always be prepared. Bring notes if needed.

5. Do not use too many exercises. Do not forget that the difficulty of the exercises should match the skill of the players.

6. Make sure you choose the right study material. Know the effectiveness of the selected drills and pay attention to the placement of the players in order when performing the drills.

7. Use positive feedback. Explain the reason for the correction

8. Be dignified. But be understanding of the players. Athletes do not always have the ability to do the right thing.

9. Have a sense of humor - be in a good mood. Remember that playing handball should be fun.

10. Don't separate the players. Note: Players react to compliments and demerits differently, and you need to approach each one individually to have the same effect.

10 TIPS FOR ATHLETES

1. Do not skip training sessions without any reason. Training is based on the participation of a certain number of players. If they are few, the exercises should be changed.

2. Do not be late for the competition. It is very unpleasant for the team to inform the tournament organizers about the lack of players on the eve of the game.

3. Get dressed and ready for practice on time. If the training plan has to be changed because the players are late, it is a very annoying situation for both the coach and the players. If you can't make it on time, call your coach and let him know.

4. Be attentive. When some players are talking about other things while explaining the drills, it takes twice as long to explain the drills because they have to be repeated. In this case, those who are listening attentively will get bored because the instructions have to be repeated. If you are on the bench during the game, use the time to study the game and decide what you will do when you get back on the field.

5. Be energetic. A tired attitude is reflected in the team. The energetic attitude is also reflected in the team. If you always try to improve yourself, you will improve.

6. Help your teammates with exercises. It's not the most fun thing to do as a defender in offensive practice, but if the defense is active, it helps the offensive player to improve. If you are a tired defender, you will teach your teammates to pass tired defenses. If you are active, you will teach your teammates to pass through active defense.

7. Stay fit even when you're injured. If you can see and hear what your teammates are practicing, you can rely on what you heard sitting on the bench. Then when you come back you know what was taught.

8. Support your teammates. To be good, you have to believe in yourself. Everyone makes mistakes and not everyone is equally qualified. If a player is always in training and what he is doing is not good enough, he loses confidence, becomes insecure and then everything goes wrong. It's better to say encouraging words to your teammate than to be reserved and criticize forever.

9. Get to know your teammates better. If you know what each player on your team can do, you can play alongside him and use his abilities to push both of you forward.

10. Use every practice game to try new and old things. Use practice games to practice, not to win. Practice games are used to test new and old things to see if they work and what needs to be improved. It is not a good idea to use such games to do things you can do, but use them to practice things you are not good at [2].

Based on the above, it can be said that the skills of the coach are seen in the effective management of the activities of the sports team, in the proper organization of training and education processes, considering the personal psychophysiological characteristics of each athlete. On the other hand, in this process, it would be appropriate if the athletes, feeling their goals and tasks, participate responsibly in the training sessions.

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